

EFFECTS OF FIBER CONTENT ON FRACTURE MECHANISMS
OF SHORT FIBER REINFORCED PET COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Effects of fiber content by volume on fracture mechanisms of short glass fiber reinforced PET (FRPET) composites are presumed by measuring the tensile strength, the parameters showing the adhesion between the fiber and the resin and the fiber orientation in the composite materials.

The presumption is verified by means of the frequency analysis of acoustic emission (AE) signals and the microfractography in this paper. It is found that the tensile strength of FRPET increases with an increase in the fiber content at the fiber content lower than 17.3 % (30 wt %) but the rate of increase in the tensile strength seems to decrease slightly with an increase in the fiber content at the fiber content higher than 17.3 %, and that the damage modes are changed from the resin cracking and the fiber debonding and pulling out, to the fiber debonding and pulling out and the fiber breakage at that content of 17.3 %.

KEYWORDS: Fracture mechanisms; Short fiber composite; Strength; Adhesion; Fiber orientation; Acoustic emission.

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently, AE methods are used in the studies on fracture mechanisms of composite materials. The AE sources which the composite materials generate in the fracture process are the resin cracking, the fiber debonding and pulling out, and the fiber breakage. Therefore, the fracture mechanisms are presumed to be based on the tensile strength of the test specimen and the adhesion between the fiber and the resin, and the fiber orientation in different fiber contents of short fiber reinforced composite materials. This presumption is confirmed by frequency analysis of AE signals and microfractography. So, the purpose of this study is to establish a guide when designing and selecting the composite materials in regards to their suitability in practical application.

2. ANALYTICAL APPROACH

The tensile strength σ_c of composite materials which all fibers of a constant length are oriented in the longitudinal direction is shown as follows;

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_{rb}V_f + \sigma_{mb}(1-V_f) \quad (1)$$

where σ_{rb} is the mean breaking stress of fibers, V_f is the fiber content by volume and σ_{mb} is the mean stress of matrix when the composite material is fractured. When the σ_{mb} is the tensile strength of matrix σ_m , the fiber length and radius are ℓ and r_f , and the σ_{rb} is proportional to ℓ/r_f , Equation (1) can be written as follows [1];

$$\sigma_c = \Phi(\ell/r_f)V_f + \sigma_m(1-V_f) \quad (2)$$

where Φ is a parameter determined by the adhesion between the fiber and the resin.

Now, when the adhesion is perfect and the short fibers are oriented in the longitudinal direction, the tensile strength σ_c is shown as follows;

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_r V_f (1-L_c/2L) + \sigma_m (1-V_f) \quad (3)$$

where σ_r is the tensile strength of fiber, L_c is a critical fiber length, and L is the mean fiber length. When $L_c/2r_f$ and $L/2r_f$ are the critical aspect ratio x_c and the mean aspect ratio x , respectively, Equation (3)

becomes [2]

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_r V_r (1 - x_c/2x) + \sigma_m (1 - V_r) \quad (4)$$

Introducing two values of $x_c=30$ [3] and $x=20$ [4] into Equation (4), the equation can be written as follows [5] ;

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_r (V_r/4) + \sigma_m (1 - V_r) \quad (5)$$

The variation of fiber length is taken into consideration in the short fiber reinforced plastics by injection molding. When the mean fiber length, the standard derivation and a parameter of fiber orientation are given by L , m , and Ψ , respectively, Equation (2) is shown as follows ;

$$\sigma_c = (\Phi \Psi / r_r) [L + (m^2/L)] V_r + \sigma_m (1 - V_r) \quad (6)$$

3. EXPERIMENTS

3.1 Test Materials The test materials are a Polyethylene Terephtharate resin with a dispersed E glass fiber. The test materials are composed of four kinds of glass fiber contents by weight, 0, 15, 30 and 45 %, respectively.

The shape and dimension of the tensile test specimen and AE test specimen are shown in Figures 1 (a) and (b), respectively. The test materials are called A, B, C and D materials, respectively. A notch length of 5 mm is cut by a fine cutter and the rest of the 0.5 mm is cut carefully by a razor in the B and D specimens in order to obtain a markedly different AE signals.

The mechanical properties of the test specimens are shown in Table 1.

3.2 Test Method The tensile test is done by using an Instron type testing machine (Shimazdu Autograph AG-10TB) at a tensile speed of 1 mm/min. The AE measuring test is done by using a tensile test machine (Shimazdu Servopulser EHF-ED10-20L) at a tensile speed of 0.2 mm/min.

AE signals are detected by a measuring apparatus (Shimazdu SAE1000A). The power spectrum is obtained by input of the AE signals recorded on a data recorder (Sony Magnescale, FMR1219) into a wave form analyzer (Analogic, DATA6000). The sensor is a wide range type, which can detect AE waves with frequencies up to 1 MHz. These sensors are used on two channels to avoid noise at the position of a specified distance from the center part of the specimen. The frequency spectrum is given in a power spectrum by using a FFT method .

A three dimensional diagram of the power spectrum, the frequency and the

load is determined. The histogram method for evaluation of the frequency components in three dimensional diagram is used [6]. The microscopic observation is executed by using a scanning electron microscope.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Effects of fiber content on parameters showing fiber orientation and adhesion between fiber and resin By introducing the value of $m \cong 1/3$ [2] into Equation (6), as it is seen that the fiber length distribution is a normal distribution, Equation (6) becomes

$$\sigma_c = 20/9 (\Phi \Psi) x V_f + \sigma_m (1 - V_f) \quad (7)$$

When all the fibers assume to be oriented in the longitudinal direction, and to be oriented at random three-dimensionally, the values of Ψ are between 0.2 and 1 in the injection molding compounds. When the longitudinal, the width and the thickness directions of specimen is x, y and z-directions, respectively, the fiber orientation angle is measured on the specimen surface of the xy plane. But, it is found that the fibers orient slightly in the xz plane. Therefore, it is assumed that the fibers in the test specimen are distributed in two-dimensions.

The parameter Ψ showing the fiber orientation is shown as follows ;

$$\Psi \equiv \bar{\sigma}_f / \sigma_f = \Sigma (\cos^4 \theta - \nu \cos^2 \theta \sin^2 \theta) \chi(\theta) \quad (8)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_f$ is the tensile strength of fibers with inclined angle θ to the longitudinal direction, ν is the Poisson's ratio of composite material and $\chi(\theta)$ is the distribution function of the fiber orientation [3]. Therefore, the values of Ψ calculated by the measured values of fiber orientation and Equation (8) are shown in Table 2.

Introducing the values of σ_f , σ_m and V_f in Table 2 into Equation (5), the values of σ_c can be calculated. The values of a parameter Φ_0 showing the ideal state which all the fibers orient in the longitudinal direction and the adhesion between the fiber and the resin is perfect can be determined by introducing the calculated values of σ_c , $x = 20$ and $\Psi = 1$ into Equation (7). Otherwise, the values of a parameter Φ showing the adhesion in the actual specimens can be determined by introducing the measured values of σ_c , x and Ψ in Table 2. The values of Φ_0 and Φ are listed in Table 2. As the relation between the tensile strength and the fiber content is shown

in Figure 2, the tensile strength increases with an increase in the fiber content at the fiber content by volume lower than 17.3 % (30 wt%) and it increases slightly at the fiber content higher than 17.3 %. This can be illustrated as follows ; As the mean fiber length and the value of Φ are relatively larger at the fiber contents lower than 17.3 %, the tensile strength increases with an increase in the fiber content though the value of Ψ is smaller. But, as the mean fiber length and the value of Φ are relatively smaller at the fiber contents higher than 17.3 %, the rate of increase in the tensile strength becomes lower though the value of Ψ is larger. Therefore, it is investigated how the change in fracture mechanisms appear at the point of 17.3 %.

4.2 Certification of change in fracture mechanisms by AE method and microfractography

Figure 3 (a) and (b) show the histogram of frequency components having an AE energy of more than 400 nV²/Hz [6]. It is thought from these figures that there are many frequency components, such as 80-130, 180-200, 250-320 and 330-410 kHz for the B material, and a few frequency components, such as 80- 200 kHz for the D material. It is considered that there is a smaller damage by resin cracking in proportion to the presence of more fibers. The power spectra at the frequency ranges of 250-320 and 360-410 kHz are larger. Therefore, it is considered that the fiber debonding and pulling out dominate the fracture process of both materials, the resin cracking follows in the B material and the fiber breakage follows in the D material. So, this suggests that there is a change in the fracture mechanisms at a fiber content by volume of 17.3 %.

Takahashi and Choi [7] reported as following : the fracture patterns differ with the surface and the interior of test specimen, the initiation and propagation of a tensile crack at the fiber end play a larger role, and the degree of this role decreases with an increase in the fiber content on the surface of test specimen. Otherwise, the shear band initiates and propagates around the fiber ends, and the shear damage between the interfaces and the fibers initiates the macroscopic fracture. It is considered that the fracture process of a short glass fiber reinforced composites is complex. However, it is found that Figure 4 (a) shows the resin cracking and the fiber debonding and pulling out of the B material, and Figure 4 (b) shows a larger amount of fiber debonding and pulling out and fiber breakage of the D material. It is considered that the resin crackings as is seen in Figure 4 (a) are few. So, it is found from observing the microfractographs that there is a change in the fracture mechanisms of short glass fiber reinforced composites according to the fiber content.

5. CONCLUSION

The change in the fracture mechanisms of short glass fiber reinforced PET composites is presumed by measuring the tensile strength, the parameters of adhesion between the fiber and the resin and the fiber orientation in the composite materials. The presumption is certificated by the AE frequency analysis and microfractography. It is found in the fracture process that there is a change in the fracture mechanisms at a fiber content of 17.3 vol% (30 wt%) and that the damage modes are changed from the resin cracking and the fiber debonding and pulling out, to the fiber debonding and pulling out and the fiber breakage at that content of 17.3 %.

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TABLE 1 MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF TEST SPECIMENS

Material	Fiber contents (wt%)	Tensile strength σ_B (MPa)	Elastic modulus E(GPa)	Poisson's ratio ν	Elongation φ (%)
A	0	57	3.5	0.44	9.8
B	15	92.2	7.0	0.43	9.1
C	30	131.5	10.8	0.43	9.6
D	45	151.5	17.4	0.40	10.0

Test speed: 1 mm/min, Temp.: $20 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, $60 \pm 5\%RH$

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 1. Shape and dimension of test specimens

TABLE 2 NUMERICAL VALUES WHICH ARE USED IN CALCULATION OF Φ AND Φ_0 , AND VALUES OF ψ

Material	V_f	σ_c (MPa)	L (mm)	x	d_f (μm)	σ_f (MPa)	σ_m (MPa)	Ψ	Φ_0 (MPa)	Φ (MPa)
B	0.079	92.2	0.29	28.4				0.539		7.53
C	0.173	131.5	0.25	24.5	10.2	3452	57	0.658	9.91	6.94
D	0.292	151.5	0.21	20.6				0.713		5.95

FIGURE 2. Relation between tensile strength and fiber content by volume

(a) B material

(b) D material

FIGURE 3. Histograms of AE frequency components

(a) B material

(b) D material

FIGURE 4. Microfractographs of B and D materials

